

IS -OPEN SOURCE- A KEYWORD FOR A SUCCESSFUL GIS DEVELOPMENT ?

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1.What is a Geographical Information System ?

A GIS can be defined as an information system capable of assembling, storing, manipulating, and displaying geographically referenced information.

GIS is also regarded as "a computer system for capturing, storing, checking, integrating, manipulating, analysing and displaying data related to positions on the Earth's surface. Typically, a Geographical Information System (or Spatial Information System) is used for handling maps of one kind or another. These might be represented as several different layers where each layer holds data about a particular kind of feature. Each feature is linked to a position on the graphical image of a map."¹²

The physical components of a GIS
Figure 1.1-Typical Components of a GIS

1.1 The basic functions of a GIS

The basic functions of a GIS are defined as¹³ capturing the data,integrating the data,projection and registration,structuring and modelling the data.The USGS web site(<http://www.usgs.gov>) defines these functions in detail as:

Data Capture:Maps can be digitized, or hand-traced with at computer mouse, to collect the coordinates of features. Data capture - putting the information into the system - is the time-consuming component of GIS work. Identities of the objects on the map must be specified, as well as their spatial relationships. Editing of information that is automatically captured can also be difficult. Electronic scanners record blemishes on a map just as faithfully as they record the map features. For example, a fleck of dirt might connect two lines that should not be connected. Extraneous data must be edited, or removed from the digital data file.

Data Integration: A GIS makes it possible to link, or integrate, information that is difficult to associate through any other means. Thus, a GIS can use combinations of mapped variables to build and analyze new variables.

Data Projection: Projection is a fundamental component of mapmaking. A projection is a mathematical means of transferring information from the Earth's three-dimensional curved surface to a two-dimensional medium - paper or a computer screen. Different projections are used for different types of maps because each projection is particularly appropriate to certain uses. Since much of the information in a GIS comes from existing maps, a GIS uses the processing power of the computer to transform digital information, gathered from sources with different projections to a common projection.

Structuring the data: Image data from a satellite that has been interpreted by a computer to produce a land use map can be "read into" the GIS in raster format. Raster data files consist of rows of uniform cells coded according to data values. An example would be land cover classification. Raster data files can be manipulated quickly by the computer, but they are often less detailed and may be less visually appealing than vector data files, which can approximate the appearance of more traditional hand-drafted maps. Vector digital data have been captured as points, lines (a series of point coordinates), or areas (shapes bounded by lines). Data restructuring can be performed by a GIS to convert data into different formats. For example, a GIS may be used to convert a satellite image map to a vector structure by generating lines around all cells with the same classification, while determining the cell spatial relationships, such as adjacency or inclusion. Geographical Information Systems are used in number of disciplines. The table below shows the areas that GIS's are used.

Archaeology Agriculture Defence	Education Landscape Architecture Law and Criminal Justice	Real Estate Retail Business
Electric and Gas Engineering/ Pipeline Engineering/ Surveying	Libraries and Museums Location Services Logistics Management	State and Local Government Telecommunications
Fire /Disaster Analysis Forestry Health Services	Marine, and Oceans Mining and Earth Sciences Natural Resources	Water and Wastewater Weather Services

Table 1.1-The Disciplines that GIS's are used.

2. Open Source in the area of Geographical Information Systems

Open source applications in the area of GIS are becoming more popular. There are 3 main resources on the web to reach information about open source GIS. These are opensourcegis.net, freegis.org and remotesensing.org. The projects, software and tools (PST) below are taken from the resources above (which are chosen from more than 200 open source gis PST). The PST below are classified and success stories about some of these PST have been mentioned in Part-3 of this document.

2.1 Open Source GIS Projects/Software & Tools

GeoTIFF(<http://www.remotesensing.org/geotiff/geotiff.html>)

GeoTIFF represents an effort by over 160 different remote sensing, GIS, cartographic, and surveying related companies and organizations to establish a TIFF based interchange format for georeferenced raster imagery.

GDAL(<http://www.remotesensing.org/gdal>)

GDAL is a translator library for raster geospatial data formats that is released under an X/MIT style Open Source license. As a library, it presents a single abstract data model to the calling application for all supported formats. The related OGR library (which lives within the GDAL source tree) provides a similar capability for simple features vector data.

LibTIFF(<http://www.libtiff.org/>)

This software provides support for the *Tag Image File Format* (TIFF), a widely used format for storing image data. Included in this software distribution is a library, libtiff, for reading and writing TIFF, a small collection of tools for doing simple manipulations of TIFF images on UNIX systems, and documentation on the library and tools. A small assortment of TIFF-related software for UNIX that has been contributed by others is also included.

Virtual Terrain Project(<http://www.vterrain.org/>)

The goal of VTP is to foster the creation of tools for easily constructing any part of the real world in interactive, 3D digital form. This goal will require a synergetic convergence of the fields of CAD, GIS, visual simulation, surveying and remote sensing. VTP gathers information and tracks progress in areas such as procedural scene construction, feature extraction, and rendering algorithms. VTP writes and supports a set of software tools (VTP Toolbox) and an interactive runtime environment (VTP Enviro). The tools and their source code are freely shared to help accelerate the adoption and development of the necessary technologies.

JPEG2000(<http://www.remotesensing.org/jpeg2000>)

JPEG2000 is a new ISO specification (ISO/IEC 15444) for a wavelet based lossy compressed format for storing images. It is intended to superceed traditional JPEG format for many applications, providing better compression and a more flexible imaging model. This site is intended to act as a focus for geospatial application of JPEG2000 format. GeoJP2™ is a format extension to JPEG2000 for embedding coordinate system and georeferencing information in a JPEG2000 JP2 format file

OpenDX(<http://www.opendx.org>)

OpenDX is a uniquely powerful, full-featured software package for the visualization of scientific, engineering and analytical data: Its open system design is built on a standard interface environments. And its sophisticated data model provides users with great flexibility in creating visualizations. With OpenDX, you can create the visualizations you want to create. OpenDX has been designed to be the place where the art of science and the science of visualization come together. It's the place where they're combined into one powerful, flexible framework that lets you "Simply Visualize."

PostGIS(<http://postgis.refractive.net>)

PostGIS adds support for geographic objects to the [PostgreSQL](#) object-relational database. In effect, PostGIS "spatially enables" the PostgreSQL server, allowing it to be used as a backend spatial database for geographic information systems (GIS), much like ESRI's SDE or Oracle's Spatial extension. PostGIS follows the OpenGIS

"Simple Features Specification for SQL" and will be submitted for compliance testing at version 1.0.

GRASS (<http://grass.itc.it/index.html>)

GRASS GIS (Geographic Resources Analysis Support System) is a Free Software Geographical Information System (GIS) with raster, topological vector, image processing, and graphics production functionality that operates on various platforms through a graphical user interface and shell in X-Windows.

MapServer(<http://mapserver.gis.umn.edu/index.html>)

MapServer is an OpenSource development environment for building spatially enabled Internet applications. The software builds upon other popular OpenSource or freeware systems like Shapelib, FreeType, Proj.4, libTIFF, Perl and others. MapServer will run where most commercial systems won't or can't, on Linux/Apache platforms. MapServer is known to compile on most UNIXes and will run under Windows NT/98/95. The MapServer system now supports MapScript which allows popular scripting languages such as Perl, Python, Tk/Tcl, and even Java to access the MapServer C API. MapScript provides a rich environment for developing applications that integrate disparate data. If the data has a spatial component and you can get to it via your favorite scripting environment then you can map it. For example, using Perl's DBI module it is possible to integrate data from just about any database vendor (eg. Oracle, Sybase, MySQL) with traditional GIS data in a single map graphics or web page. In addition, there is now a PHP/MapScript module included in the current release.

GpsDrive (<http://www.kraftvoll.at/software/>)

GpsDrive is a car (bike, ship, plane) navigation system. GpsDrive displays your position provided from your NMEA capable GPS receiver on a zoomable map, the map file is autoselected depending of the position and preferred scale.

Gen2shp(<http://intevation.de/~jan/gen2shp/gen2shp.html>)

Gen2shp is a simple C-Program which can read the format required by the ESRI ArcInfo generate command.

MapIt! (<http://www.mapit.de/index.en.html>)

MapIt! is a serverside web-application for rastermaps. Navigation and points of interests are easily configured. Compatible with all Web-Server using CGI.

OpenMap (<http://openmap.bbn.com/>)

OpenMap is a Java Beans based toolkit for building applications and applets needing geographic information. Using OpenMap components, you can access data from legacy applications, in-place, in a distributed setting. At its core, OpenMap is a set of Swing components that understand geographic coordinates. These components help you show map data, and help you handle user input events to manipulate that data.

GeoTools(<http://www.geotools.org>)

GeoTools is a Java based mapping toolkit that allows Maps to be viewed interactively on web browsers without the need for dedicated server side support.

GIS Viewer (<http://elib.cs.berkeley.edu/gis/>)

GIS Viewer 4.0 is a new web-based tool for displaying and manipulating layers of geographical points and vectors, and raster data such as maps and images. GIS Viewer 4.0 is designed to scale from data sets covering the entire earth to high-resolution imagery of fine details. It has many applications, from locating, annotating, and sharing information about interesting features of the large geographic data sets, to presenting geopositioned data sets in useful contexts, to allowing users to pan and zoom museum image collections.

Gpspoint(<http://scampi.physik.uni-konstanz.de/~tschank/gpspoint/>)

Program to download and upload waypoints, routes, and tracks to and from your GPS device. Upload and download is possible via the GARMIN interface. Current position obtainable via the NMEA Interface, supported by most GPS devices.

MITAB(<http://pages.infinet.net/danmo/e00/index-mitab.html>)

MITAB is a C++ library to read and write MapInfo .TAB (binary) and .MIF/MID files. It is based on the OGR library which is an implementation of the Open GIS Consortium Simple Feature specification.

Terravision(<http://www.tvgeo.com/>)

TerraVision™ is an Open Source distributed, interactive terrain visualization system developed by SRI International. It allows users to navigate, in real time, through a 3-D graphical representation of a real landscape created from elevation data and aerial images of that landscape. TerraVision™ can browse huge datasets, in the order of terabytes, and all data can be distributed over multiple servers across the Web. 3-D VRML and GeoVRML models can be overlaid, e.g. buildings, wind vectors, etc. and TerraVision can access OGC Web Map Servers (WMS)

Deegree(<http://deegree.sourceforge.net/>)

Deegree is a Java framework for geospatially-enabled solutions. It is based on common GI standards and allows building applications with spatially referenced content. Deegree components can be used to either develop a standalone desktop mapping solution to be locally installed on a users machine, or to set up a highly distributed and service-based infrastructure.

DEMViewer (<http://www.geogr.uni-jena.de/~p6taug/demviewer/>)

DEMViewer is a digital elevation model viewer for ArcGrid ASCII export files. With DEMViewer you can visualize digital elevation models generated by ArcInfo and combine it with data (in the same ArcGrid ASCII export format and/or Jpeg/Gif images).

QGIS (Quantum GIS) (<http://qgis.sourceforge.net/>)

Quantum GIS (QGIS) is designed to be a Geographic Information System (GIS) built for Linux/Unix. QGIS will offer support for vector and raster formats and provide a comprehensive GIS. It is based on the GUI toolkit Qt.

Geoserver (<http://geoserver.sourceforge.net/>)

The GeoServer project is a Java (J2EE) implementation of the OpenGIS Consortium's Web Feature Server specification. It is free software, available under the GPL 2.0 license. Users who would like to access their geographic data over the Internet using flexible, industry-approved standards should take a look at GeoServer or one of the existing commercial Web Feature Servers.

Mdb2shapefile(<http://www.linkgeo.com.br/enus/download.php?file=3>)

Mdb2shapefile is a GUI for exporting data of an Access table to a ShapeFile table(DBF).

GISAR (<http://gisar.sourceforge.net/ENG/Index.htm>)

GISAR is a 2D,3D dynamic model of real objects (streets, houses, telephones, etc), that may be used for development any functional and visual models of real system. At present it used for automate working of telecommunication station.

GML4J(<http://gml4j.sourceforge.net/>)

GML4J is a Java API for facilitating work with the Geography Markup Language. GML is an XML-based framework for encoding geography information adopted as a recommendation paper by OGC.

OpenSVGMapServer (http://www.carto.net/projects/open_svg_mapserver/)

OpenSVGMapServer 1.01 is a free, open source set of scripts that, run on a web

server, will dynamically generate vector map files from spatial data in a database. The scripts are in the PHP scripting language and are designed for use with a MySQL database. The data generated are in scaleable vector graphic (SVG) format, with attribute data in the form of ecmascript/Javascript arrays. The files can be viewed through the Internet Explorer web browser with the SVG .

DXF Import, Manipulation, and Export Library (<http://www.coin3d.org/Dime>)

Dime is a C++ class library for reading, constructing, manipulating, and writing DXF file data. The name is an acronym for **DXF** **I**mport, **M**anipulation, and **E**xport library. Dime is known to compile on Win32, Linux, IRIX, HP-UX, Solaris, BeOS and MacOS.

GeoVRML (<http://www.geovrml.org/>)

GeoVRML 1.1 provides a suite of solutions for representing and visualizing geographic data using a standard VRML97 (Virtual Reality Modeling Language) browser.

Visible Earth Project (<http://visibleearth.nasa.gov/>)

The purpose of NASA's Visible Earth is to provide a consistently updated, central point of access to the superset of NASA's Earth science-related images, animations, and data visualizations. These images are considered to be public domain and, as such, are freely available to the interested public-at-large, the media, scientists, and educators for re-use and/or re-publication.

3.Success Stories About Open Source GIS

3.1 The Classification

Before starting the sucess stories it is better to classify the open source GIS software listed above.

Standardisation	Data sharing and transfer	Visualisation Projects/Libraries
GeoTIFF JPEG2000 GML4J GeoVRML	GDAL LibTIFF Gen2shp MITAB Mdb2shapefile DIME	Virtual Terrain Project OpenDX Terravision DEMViewer Visible Earth Project
Base GIS	Web Mapping	GPS
GRASS QGIS GISAR	MapServer MapIt! OpenMap GeoTools GIS Viewer Deegree Geoserver OpenSVGMapServer	GpsDrive Gpspoint
		DB Support for Spatial Data
		PostGIS

Table 3.1-Open Source GIS PST

3.2 Success Stories

3.2.1 Standardisation Tools & Formats

As mentioned in their web site ¹ "The GeoTIFF format is completely open, public domain, non-proprietary. It was produced by Dr. Niles Ritter, while at NASA-JPL (Jet Propulsion Laboratory), and changes, or additions to the format are proposed through a public review using email and WWW resources. Two meetings of developers from all areas of the geographic information processing industry have lead to proposals for revision, since early 1994. There is no restriction on licensing, implementation, promulgation, or any uses of the format. The format is entirely open, and available to all. The specifications are public, there are abundant free software source libraries, toolkits, data samples, and technical support through the email forum." The SPOT Image Corp ,Trifid Space Imaging ,US Geological Survey ,New York Department of Transportation have an intention of delivering data on GeoTIFF format.

Kadaku Software² is developing a SDK for JPEG2000 the new open source JPEG standart.Aware Inc ³ has developed a codec for JPEG2000.

Galdos Systems Inc has developed the GML4Java tool and they are still providing tools and services for GML related software.They state that ⁴ "by GML we will able to access geographic information about any place, anywhere in the world and we will get driving instructions, checking land parcel boundaries, or querying the path of an underground cable from our PDA, cell phone or desktop computer."

GeoVRML is an official Working Group of the Web3D Consortium. It was formed on 27 Feb 1998 with the goal of developing tools and recommended practice for the representation of geographical data using the Virtual Reality Modeling Language (VRML).The name of the modelling language(or standard) is the same as the group name and it is GeoVRML.Until now ESRI's ArcInfo/ArcView 8.1,Bashir's Research ShapeViz,DEM2GeoEG converter for USGS DEMs,Tile Set Manager API (tsmApi) library,SRI International's Web Map Server (WMS) have added support for GeoVRML .

3.2.2 Data Sharing and Transfer

GDAL library is used by Grass A raster/vector open source GIS.Grass uses GDAL for raster import OpenEV exclusively uses GDAL for raster access.UMN MapServer the popular web mapping application has GDAL support. The VTP libraries now use GDAL. Cadcorp SIS is a Windows GIS has recently implemented a GDAL plugin FME is a GIS translator package includes a GDAL plugin ,and MS MacroSystem 3D DEM Viewer uses GDAL library.

Gen2Shp converter is a commonly used tool in ESRI-ArcView community.It is used for converting raw GPS data to .shp/.shx.dbf files or converting generate format to the .shp/.shx/dbf files.

MITAB library can also be used to read data from MapInfo files and also to create them.

GEHydro⁵ uses DIME to read/write .dxf files in their products like GEHydro Optimizer.

3.2.3 Visualisation Tools

Many places have been modelled under virtual terrain project as VTP demo cities including Hangzhou-China, Island of Hawaii, and Silicon Valley-CA, and New York.

OpenDx⁶ is developed by IBM Research. Visualization and Imagery Solutions, Inc. provides training, support, and consulting for IBM's Visualization Data Explorer product and the new OpenDX open source project. VGI Vision Group International Inc. provides custom data modelling services using IBM Visualization Data Explorer (DX), a powerful data visualization software package.

SRI International (the developers of TerraVision)⁷ was awarded a subcontract for .6 million from the U.S. Defense Advanced Research Projects Agency (DARPA) for its role in MAGIC-II, a collaborative three-year project involving industry, academia and government. MAGIC-II, a follow-on to the original MAGIC project (MAGIC-I), will address scaling issues in state-of-the-art networks that support widely distributed data handling systems and applications. SRI's role in the MAGIC-II collaboration is to develop a new three-dimensional terrain visualization application, called TerraVision II, that will use widely distributed stored and real-time data to visualize a variety of data types such as maps, weather, and satellite and aerial imagery. Users can work on high-performance workstations connected to a high-speed network or on mobile workstations connected via wireless links.

3.2.4 Base GIS

Grass is the most commonly used open source GIS. There are currently 5 international user groups for GRASS. Grass is commercially supported by firms from Canada, Russia, Thailand, U.K., U.S.A. and Denmark. Web based Tourist GIS of North Idaho region is structured on GRASS. Landslide Database at Osaka City University is also based on GRASS. The Hydrologic Unit Model for the United States, an online water resources project is another example using GRASS.

GISAR is used for automating the working of a telecommunication station in Russia.

3.2.5 Web Mapping

Map server is one of the most commonly used open source mapping server all over the world. On their application gallery⁸ there are more than 100 sites listed as map server users. Map server can be used as a basic CGI based map server, but also it has some extended versions with java support. Some of the sites that use map server can be found below:

Atlas of Canada (<http://atlas.gc.ca>) - The Atlas of Canada provides authoritative, current and accessible geographic information products at a national level. Working with partners, the Atlas facilitates the integration and analysis of diverse data in order to increase overall knowledge about Canada. Provider: Canada Centre for Remote Sensing, Natural Resources Canada.

Digital Chart of the World (<http://mapserver.socialchange.net.au/world>) Digital Map of the World examples from Australia. Provider: Social Change Online, Australia

Estrada Real, Brazil (http://ils.io.inf.br/ier_map/ierf.htm) A MapServer application in Brazil. Provider: Instituto Estrada Real, Brazil

Flood Hazard Maps for River Mosel (<http://www.gefahrenatlas-mosel.de/>)

An application using MapServer with a javascript client on Windows 2000 each module. Provider: NETGIS, Gesellschaft für Geoinformation und Multimedia, Germany

HALgis(<http://halgis.halle.de>) - Online-GIS-Infos from the City of Halle (Saale) in Germany: with Cityplan, WalkingRoute, Building sites and Diversions, Ortho Photos, Adress-Search. Provider: IT-Consult Halle GmbH, Stadt Halle (Saale).

As mentioned in OpenMap web site⁹ [MAYA Viz](#) has used OpenMap to create GIS visualization tools built upon [CoMotion](#), their distributed data analysis platform. In CoMotion, users can work with maps as well as charts, tables, and other frames to collaboratively analyze and manipulate information. [GeoVirgil](#), by Steve McDonald, is a map program that directly reads in NASA's [PDS format](#). With it, you can load [hundreds of CDs](#) from NASA and explore Venus, the Earth, our Moon and Mars. It also provides some image processing and drawing capabilities so you can create maps. Platte River Associates, Inc., a provider of petroleum systems modeling software and services, is using OpenMap as a graphical interface for querying a worldwide heat flow database, assembled by Pollack, Hurter, and Johnson on their web site. The applet is offered as a free service to users who fill out a brief form. Their modifications to OpenMap have been [published on their web site](#), as well.

Geotools¹⁰ is the most commonly used client side web mapping application. Moreland, the property development company of the Tongaat Hulett Group, and one of South Africa's leading land developers, has since 1997 had a website www.moreland.co.za, which has featured its vast portfolio. However, the site has never been truly interactive in the sense that visitors to the site have not been able to glean more than a paragraph of information on each development, and have then had to request further information from the respective contact person. This has all changed though, as Moreland have embarked upon a project whereby its GIS (Geographic Information System) data is provided over the Internet by Geotools, allowing browsers to study detailed information pertinent to each development. The interactivity of Geotools has been extended by the author's applet ([Umit Isikdag Clickable Map Applet](#)) which added support for custom shaded maps and ability to get a value from a database by clicking on a map area. British Library also uses GeoTools at its map kiosks.

The Museum of Vertebrate Zoology¹¹ is a center for research on, conservation of, and education in terrestrial vertebrates. The center uses GISViewer to show its maps. Alaska University Museum is also another user of GISViewer tool.

4. Discussion

In this section we will try to answer the question if open source is a keyword for the development of a successful geographical information system.

The first issue is that there are more than one data model (raster, vector, tin, object etc.) and many data formats to represent geographical data and information. The GIS specialists face the problem of data conversion. Most of the common software have some conversion utilities but open source conversion utilities, API's and libraries play a big role on data conversion. In this issue open source software and tools are not the only key actors but it can be said that they are very useful.

Today global economy forces organisations to use interoperable software. The interoperability will have an high importance in the future of GIS. Interoperable software exchanges data by common data and information exchange standards. By

using these standards data and information models are developed. The data and information models are developed as open source models to enable effective data and information exchange. In the context of interoperability open source is a must.

Distributed computing gives us new opportunities and power on analysing and visualising spatial (raster/vector) data. The use of open source in distributed computing projects will increase the trust of project participants.

GIS plays an important role on e-government and e-municipality activities. By the use of open source GIS the expenses on information systems of e-government projects will be extremely reduced.

Geographical Information Systems are used in the universities for educational purposes and for research. Open source GIS will enable universities to use the software at no cost and will give the opportunity of developing new geographical information systems and system components tailored for public and private sectors.

The trend for using a web based geographical information systems is increasing, especially (in e-government projects) to give citizens better services about census data, location, touristic GIS, and cadastral surveys.

As a result geographical information systems are becoming a very important part of our lives, and open source can not be seen as the only key for the development of a successful GIS, but the use of open source software will bring many advantages that will lead us to develop well formed, interoperable, interactive, distributed geographical information systems. Open source is the hidden source/force that will lead our systems to excellence.

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